

LIFE
ALNUS

LAYMAN'S REPORT

Conservation, restoration and governance
of Mediterranean riparian forests

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1.

THE LIFE ALNUS PROJECT

The Segre River in Cerdanya county is one of the best examples in Catalonia of a river free of artificial obstacles / Photo: Jordi Bas.

1. THE LIFE ALNUS PROJECT

LIFE ALNUS is a project for the conservation, restoration and governance of alder forests and other related riparian forests, such as willow, poplar, ash and elm forests, or mixed forests of alders, willows, ashes, elms and poplars. It is co-funded by the LIFE Nature and Biodiversity Programme of the European Union, which includes the improvement of habitats and species of the Natura 2000 Network.

The Natura 2000 Network protects the most important natural areas in the European Union. These areas contain habitats and species of flora and fauna of community importance due to their precarious state of conservation.

LIFE ALNUS river basins with the current and potential distribution of riparian vegetation. Source: MN Consultors.

European alder (*Alnus glutinosa*) / Photo: Jordi Bas.

* 91E0* priority habitat: Alluvial forests with *Alnus glutinosa* and *Fraxinus excelsior* (*Alno-Padion*, *Alnion incanae*, *Salicion albae*).

The purpose of the project

The conservation of riparian forests poses a major scientific, social and political challenge for Europe which, to date, has only been addressed through one-off, local restoration projects. In other words, there has not yet been a European project with an integrated, cross-cutting approach to the conservation of riparian forests at a regional or national scale. This situation would not be serious if the evolution of the riparian forest habitat were positive after 30 years of the Habitats Directive. However, this is not the case: for the European Mediterranean region as a whole, the conservation status of riparian forests has shifted from inadequate to bad between 2007 and 2018, according to the European Commission.

This is the challenge facing LIFE ALNUS. The project has been implemented in three pilot basins (Besòs, Ter and Segre), covering more than 1,000 linear kilometres. The three basins encompass more than 50.5% of the geographical distribution of Catalonia's alder forests. It should be highlighted that the Spanish section of the Natura 2000 Network contains 48% of the surface area of alder forests in the Mediterranean region. This means that Spain (and, in turn, Catalonia, with almost 15% of the aforementioned surface area) bears a significant amount of responsibility for the conservation of this habitat in Mediterranean Europe.

Catalonia is home to a great diversity of riparian forests, from headwater alder forests to willow, poplar and alder forests on alluvial plains. The great valleys and plains are precisely where these habitats are most degraded and fragmented, to such an extent that it is estimated that more than 80% of the riparian forests of the European alluvial plains have been lost. Due to their critical conservation status throughout Europe, alder forests and other riparian forests have been classified as habitats of community importance in the Habitats Directive of the European Union.

Catalonia is probably one of the European biogeographical regions with the greatest potential for improving the conservation status of its habitat, but at the same time it faces some of the most difficult conservation challenges, which means that the experience acquired through this project, transferable to other basins, serves as a valuable example of what can be done. Moreover, Catalonia forms part of the Mediterranean front where alder forests will have to adapt to more intense and recurring periods of drought as a result of climate change.

Preparatory actions

Action A1. Preliminary studies for the planning of conservation actions

In order to approach the conservation of alder forests strategically at the basin scale, it was necessary to determine the conservation status of the riparian forests in the three ALNUS basins (Segre, Ter and Besòs). From the inception of the project, work was carried out to diagnose and understand the causes of habitat loss, in order to systematically plan where it was most important to act. Since economic and human resources tend to be limited, it was necessary to decide in which river stretches (divided into units of approximately 500 linear metres) conservation or recovery actions could be most efficient:

1. Stretches where the habitat was fragmented and the continuity of the forest could be restored.
2. Stretches where the habitat had disappeared and there was significant potential for its reintroduction.
3. Stretches with underdeveloped vegetation, with many sprouting trees, where silvicultural work could be carried out to improve the vigour and heterogeneity of trees.

1. Stretches with the presence of non-native plant species, especially those of an invasive nature. The selected stretches had to be ones in which these non-native species were not dominant but rather scattered in small groups within communities dominated by native species. This ensured the optimisation of results (low cost/benefit).
2. Stretches and river courses with alder forests and other fluvial habitats of community importance located beyond the Natura 2000 Network. Priority was given to alder forests on the alluvial plain, which are the ones that have disappeared the most since ancient times.

As a whole, they were stretches which together contained a combination of problems, which had not deteriorated excessively and which offered great potential for recovery, ensuring a cost-effective benefit for nature.

More than 1000 river kilometres were analysed between the three basins of the ALNUS project. Only 316 hectares of alder forests were mapped (184 hectares in the Segre, 106 hectares in the Ter and 26 hectares in the Besòs). This figure was much lower than expected on the basis of previous data. In addition, 2043 hectares of riparian forest with the presence of alder and 432 hectares of willow forests and mixed forests without alders were mapped.

Action A2. Habitat conservation and restoration plans

Following the diagnosis, riparian forest conservation plans were drawn up for each basin. These plans prioritised stretches in which to intervene on the basis of the diagnosed problems. Interventions in the high-priority stretches were carried out by LIFE ALNUS. Interventions will be carried out in other stretches in the near future, through new projects.

An integrated vision of the restoration of fluvial habitats (understood as the area encompassing the river and the riparian forest) entails the renaturalisation of the dynamics, processes and flows that govern them, as well as removing the hydromorphological or chemical barriers, disconnections and discontinuities that prevent the integrity of the basin continuum from being maintained.

Picture of the hydromorphological restoration carried out in the fluvial island of Les Gambires (Ter River, municipality of Les Masies de Voltregà, Catalonia). 2022 July. The good health of the lateral connectivity resulting from the river restoration can be verified, where a flow of 3 m³/s circulates in the dry season. Photo: David Estany.

1. Invasive species elimination and control measures	3. Measures to restore the longitudinal continuity of the habitat
2. Forest management measures	4. Habitat reintroduction in courses where it became extinct

Example of the methodology followed to design the strategy of the Habitat Restoration and Conservation Plans for each LIFE ALNUS basin. The conservation action consisted of identifying the best-preserved river stretches or those with the greatest potential for restoration in which to expand the Natura 2000 Network. The restoration was based on four actions: 1) elimination and control of exotic species; 2) improvement of the structure of the riparian forest with silvicultural treatments; 3) defragmentation of the habitat through planting; and 4) reintroduction of the habitat in stretches where it has disappeared. The spatial planning of each action started from the analysis of alternatives: a) by means of suitability or importance indices of each stretch; b) using prioritisation models based on systematic planning (Marxan conservation planning software). The map in the attached figure represents the resulting model for the reintroduction of riparian forest. The stretches that were initially identified for their strategic interest were then studied in more detail through fieldwork and reviewed by the partners responsible for (and knowledgeable about) each basin. The purpose of all this was to make the final selection of the stretches in which to carry out the intervention would take place. Once the stretches were selected, the work was carried out on the ground: homogenous surfaces (stands) were distinguished where actions were planned, the vegetation was inventoried and the possibilities of intervention were analysed based on their ecological characteristics and other social-legal aspects. Source: MN Consultors / CTFC.

Action A3. Land Agreements with the owners

In order to protect, improve and conserve riparian forests, it was necessary to reach so-called river stewardship agreements with various types of landowner: individuals, companies, public authorities, etc.

Over the course of the project, agreements have been reached with 17 private landowners and three public landowners, including a hydroelectric company.

Signing of a river stewardship agreement with the owner of the Can Batista estate (Ter basin, Torelló) in 2021, as part of the LIFE ALNUS project / Photo: Marc Ordeix.

Conservation actions

The project was based on the premise that the best option for the restoration of fluvial areas is the recovery of natural dynamics; that is, enabling the river to regulate itself through the recovery of flows and the dynamics of sediments and the flooding regime. This passive restoration strategy can be implemented when the impact factors have disappeared or decreased significantly. However, this is not always possible. Therefore, the ultimate goal of the project is to implement active restoration actions that facilitate the recovery of natural processes, thus enabling the river to organise itself. Accordingly, the fluvial system is improved through the removal of dams and barriers, the restoration of flows and the elimination of invasive species, while the structure of the forest is improved through silvicultural work and planting.

Action C1. Improved protection of riparian forests

The LIFE ALNUS project completes the Catalan strategy for the conservation of riparian forests by strengthening the improvement and expansion of the Natura 2000 Network. Despite the great effort that has been made in Catalonia to cover 31% of the territory within the Natura 2000 Network, there were still river courses and/or alder forests and other riparian habitats of community importance in the ALNUS basins that were underrepresented and outside the legal protection area of the Natura 2000 Network. Accordingly, the project worked in close collaboration with the Directorate General for Environmental Policies and the Natural Environment (DGPA) of the Government of Catalonia, which is the body responsible for planning the Natura 2000 Network in Catalonia.

The selection of areas began during the preparatory actions and ended with the administrative procedures initiated by the DGPA. An innovative component of the action was the participatory process carried out with the competent public authorities and the territorial and social stakeholders. The purpose was to achieve as great a consensus as possible with the local population. As a final result, plans have been put in place to extend the Natura 2000 Network to the fluvial areas of the Segre, Ter and Besòs basins by around 970 ha. Among them, 81 ha concern to the expansion of current SAC and 889 ha to new SAC declared.

Location map of the fluvial-riparian areas included in the proposal for the extension of the Natura 2000 Network. Source: Natural Environment Planning Service, Government of Catalonia.

Action C2. Restoration of riparian vegetation

In the case of riparian forests, it is important to recover the lost continuity of the habitat, since this continuity makes it possible to foster ecological connectivity. LIFE ALNUS has implemented actions to restore deteriorated sections of the riparian forest that still offer optimal potential for recovery. These sections have been identified as priority areas in the conservation plans. The actions have focused on four aspects:

1. The reconnection of the fluvial continuum (defragmentation of the habitat).
2. The reintroduction of the habitat in sub-basins and extensive stretches in which it has disappeared.
3. The control of exotic species.
4. The improvement of the complexity of the structure of the forest, along with its maturity and biodiversity.

The reconnection and reintroduction of the habitat was carried out by means of the planting of indigenous woody species, in the form of seedlings or starter plants (using stakes), gathered from the basin itself. The control of exotic species was carried out using the best possible practices, prioritising the felling and tree injection of invasive vegetation in places where native woody vegetation could easily reclaim and cover the area. Good forest management practices were applied, consisting of the selection of shoots, selective felling, the production of dead wood by ringing or felling trees, where it was in short supply. Hydromorphological restoration work was occasionally carried out to recover old river branches that had disappeared. Finally, the remains from felling were used to build otter dens.

Plant production for LIFE ALNUS at the public enterprise Forestal Catalana nursery, in Breda (Vallès Oriental county). Alder seed saplings (like those in the image), European and narrow-leaved ashes, poplar, elder, and dogwood, among others, were obtained. Also white, purple, bitter and grey willows were produced from stakes. The fruits and cuttings were collected in the same basin, from trees and bushes close to where the riparian forest restoration projects were carried out. The aim was for the plantation to be from the same genetic population. Thus, genetic variability was preserved and at the same time, a better adaptation of the plants was achieved / Photo: Jordi Camprodon.

Selected felling in an old plane forest in order to recover the natural riparian vegetation. Certain large plane trees that compete with the ashes, maples and lindens are selected for felling. Other plane trees are left alone because they provide shade for the stream, protect the riverbanks and/or host many threatened species. The black locust trees are all felled because of their invasive nature. Sora Stream (Ter basin), Montesquiu Castle Park / Photo: Jordi Camprodon.

Action C3.Pilot projects

River ecosystem restoration projects were carried out in each ALNUS basin, comprising innovative actions whose successes and failures would be useful for the design and implementation of future projects in Catalan basins and those of the European Mediterranean region as a whole.

The actions consisted of restoring and facilitating natural dynamics. Within each basin, stretches were selected that contained an adequate representation of the various problems affecting Mediterranean alder forests on alluvial plains. These stretches required innovative, elaborate technical approaches due to a series of complex features, such as deep incisions, a high degree of deterioration or the strong regulation of the hydrological regime.

The pilot projects were as follows:

Pilot project 1) Removal and reduction of barriers, and restoration of the habitat that had disappeared in the built-up stretch of the Congost River (Besòs basin) in the conurbation of Granollers. Reintroduction of the alder forest. SAC Riu Congost. 72 ha. / Photo: Jordi Bas.

Pilot project 2) Restoration of the hydromorphological dynamics of sediments and removal of barriers on two river islands of the middle course of the Ter River. Les Gambires and Sorral Islands (Torelló-Masies de Voltregà). Future SAC Meandres del Ter. 19.2 ha. / Photo: Jordi Camprodon.

Pilot project 3) Restoration of hydromorphological processes and of an alder forest on the alluvial plain of the Segre River. Gallissà Pounds, Segre River, Bellver de Cerdanya. SAC Riberes de l'Alt Segre. 4.5 ha. / Photo: Jordi Bas.

Pilot project 4) Recovery of flows downstream from two locks used for the hydroelectric exploitation of the Ter River, a highly regulated river in hydromorphological terms. Dams of El Mariner (Camprodon) and Gallifa (Masies de Voltregà), Ter River, managed by the company Estabanell y Pahisa, SA. SAC Riberes de l'Alt Ter and future SAC Meandres del Ter. / Photo: Jordi Bas.

Action c4. Regulating public use

Visiting river sites is a typical recreational activity that should be encouraged. However, we frequently come across situations that make regulation and intervention necessary in order to improve the quality of rivers and streams and their forests. As such, with the help of various groups, hikers, fishing enthusiasts and naturalists, a series of guidelines and recommendations have been drawn up to facilitate a better environmental use of riparian forests.

Sports fishing sites have been determined in agreement with local fishing organisations. On the other hand, a Permanent Fishing Refuge was declared in the river Ter, between the municipalities of Torelló and Masies de Voltregà. It includes the islands of Les Gambires and El Sorral (pilot project C3). This set of actions cover 160 ha.

Section of the *Camí vora Ges* (Ges Riverside Path), a project implemented in the 1990s by the Grup de Defensa del Ter (Ter River Protection Group), aimed at enabling the public to rediscover the river / Photo: Jordi Camprodon.

Management guidelines

One of the main products of LIFE ALNUS was the edition of the *Technical handbook for the conservation and restoration of riparian areas*. The handbook collects the different experiences of the project. It includes technical guidelines for sustainable forest management of riparian forests. On the other hand, a document was drawn up with technical prescriptions for the treatment of plant remains after floods. Its purpose is to contribute to the governance and good practices of river areas.

Governance

We aim to raise awareness about the social importance of restoring riparian forests, both as green infrastructures and as sites of important environmental, cultural and experiential values. Furthermore, we aim to inform and raise the awareness of landowners and land managers about new habitat management criteria.

A process for the improvement of governance has been undertaken using an approach based on discussion rooms with different groups. These groups were established in order to discuss and reach a consensus that reconciles the environmental values, economic activities and social uses of fluvial areas. The discussion rooms hosted managers of natural areas, forestry professionals, hydraulic engineers, owners of rural estates with riparian areas, local councillors, representatives of hydroelectric and extractive companies, naturalist, ecological and/or land stewardship associations, and groups that organise recreational river activities. Each discussion room drew up a list of ten actions to be implemented, agreed upon by all the participants and available to view on the LIFE ALNUS website.

To achieve as much public awareness of the project as possible, various tools have been used, including social networks, a newsletter, an exhibition, environmental education activities, posters, handbooks, etc. All these materials are available on the website: www.lifealnus.eu.

Ecological monitoring

Various hydromorphological indicators (flows, topography, sediments) and biological indicators (aquatic macroinvertebrates, fish, riparian flora and vegetation, riparian birds, and semi-aquatic and riparian mammals) have been monitored. Through an initial extensive sampling process, the association was established between the bioindicators and the complexity of the riparian forest structure. The second goal of monitoring was to evaluate, in the short and long term, the response of the hydromorphological and biological indicators to the habitat improvement and restoration actions. Finally, the results and conclusions, derived both from the previous studies and from the monitoring of bioindicators, have provided basic information to be integrated in the planning of the actions of the LIFE ALNUS project, and in adaptive management plans to enable its replicability in other river basins.

Scientific sampling of fish by means of electric fishing in the Ter River in Les Masies de Voltregà by the team of the Centre for the Study of Mediterranean Rivers - University of Vic - Central University of Catalonia. October 2021 / Photo: Pol Guardis.

In the Besòs basin, hydromorphological monitoring corroborate the recovery of fluvial dynamics (removal of the river's longitudinal and transverse barriers). In the case of the Ter River, the hydromorphological restoration of Les Gambires Island recovered the flow of the secondary channels of the river. Before the restoration actions, the channels were disconnected and were dry due to flows lower than 33 m³/s. Water only circulated the 8 % of days a year. Right after the restoration, the water began to circulate continuously, even at low flows. The actions improved the pre-existing lateral and vertical connectivity problems (flow – piezometric level relationship). In this way, the relationship between the river and the shoreline was favoured.

Image of Gambires island in 2022, before the works were undertaken. The orange line shows the border of the scope of influence of the piezometric level at the lower end of the island with the dam. This has facilitated good development of the riparian forest in this area. The orange dot shows the location of the piezometer. B) The relationship between the flow rate and piezometric level pre- and post-intervention. Before the restoration works, we can see that, for low flow rates ($Q < 5 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$), the piezometric level was controlled by the dam and, indirectly, from the water collected by the catchment channels of the Gambires dam. After completion of the works, the piezometric level at the monitoring sensor is higher (30 cm, approx.) for low flow rates. In this case, the piezometric level of the whole island is controlled by the secondary branch.

The communities of macroinvertebrates and fish, as well as the aquatic habitats, improved in the Segre, the Ter and the Besòs rivers, after the pilot restoration actions (action C3). On the other hand, the correct application of environmental flows by the hydroelectric company Estabanell y Pahisa SA, resulted in a greater number of Mediterranean barbel and larger sizes.

Preservation of threatened species & singular elements

Complex vertical stratification

Naturalness of the fluvial space

Defragmentation & breadth of the forest

Key elements for riparian biodiversit

Diversity of mesohabitats

Flow recovery

Tree diversity, large and old trees, dead wood

Elements to take into consideration in order to improve the biodiversity of riparian forests.

The improvement of the naturalness of the river will allow an increase in the richness of species, a greater complexity of the habitat and, therefore, a greater resilience to global change. LIFE ALNUS demonstrated the influence of recurrent droughts on alder decline, which can be related to climate change. The best forest management practices applied in the basin as a whole, on the one hand, and the natural progression of forests towards more mature systems, would reduce evapotranspiration, increase the flow of watercourses and facilitate the resilience of alders and other riparian flora.

The quality of the riparian vegetation has been determined through the Fluvial Vegetation Index (FVI). Described in the HIDRI protocol of the Catalan Water Agency, which has been drawn up for the assessment of the hydromorphological quality of rivers (Munné et al., 2006), this index assesses the state of conservation of riverbanks by using riparian vegetation as a bioindicator of their naturalness.

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The headwaters of the Segre and Ter are the ALNUS basins with the greatest floristic richness and structural complexity. However, the middle Ter and the Besòs, despite their higher degree of anthropic transformation, preserve some sections of the riverside forest that are in a moderate good state of conservation and with a medium-high biological diversity: flora, vegetation, birds and mammals. The best stands conserved in the three basins are small and scattered, due to the disappearance or degradation of most of the riparian habitats. The bioindicators were related in a statistically significant way with the density of large trees and the diversity of trees, among other characteristics of the habitat, according to the taxa analysed. The human footprint, such as proximity to infrastructure, influenced the distribution of some groups.

Multivariate statistical models (GLMM) have been made to determine how different groups of animals prefer or avoid various elements of the habitat. The table below provides a summary, indicating whether the relationship is positive or negative, along with the level of significance: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Tree cover (4-16 m): percentage of plant cover, typically wooded, between 4 and 16 m high. Large trees (> 47.5 cm): density of trees greater than 47.5 cm of DBH (trunk diameter) in trees/ha. Undergrowth (1-4 m): percentage of undergrowth cover (shrubs, lianas and small trees) between 1 and 4 m high. Tree diversity: Shannon's index for tree species. Fluvial nature: absence of infrastructure (breakwaters, locks, bridges), tested only in terrestrial and semi-aquatic carnivores. Landscape diversity: Shannon index in a 500 m buffer. Proximity to anthropogenic covers: distance to built-up areas and main roads. Native predators: abundance of native carnivores (beech marten, common genet, badger and fox). Non-native predators: abundance of non-native carnivores (American mink, domestic cat and dog).

Selected element of the habitat	Forest birds	Cavity birds ¹	Arboreal bats ²	Bat's richness	Forest carnivorous ³	Small mammals ⁴
Vegetal cover (4-16 m)		**			*	
Large trees (> 47,5 cm)	**	**	*	*		
Understory (1-4 m)				*	*	
Tree diversity			***	*		
Fluvial naturality						*
Landscape diversity				**		
Anthropic cover proximity	***				***	
Native predators						*
Alien predators						*

■ positive relationship ■ negative relationship

¹ *Sitta europaea*, *Certhia brachydadya*, tits, ² *Nyctalus leisleri*, *Nyctalus cf. lasiopterus*, *Myotis crypticus*, *Barbastella barbastellus*. ³ *Genetta genetta*, *Martes foina*, *Meles meles*. ⁴ *Arvicola sapidus*, *Neomys* sp.

The survival of the seedlings and stem cuttings implanted in the restoration was variable depending on the place and the weather conditions (very dry summers). The survival change between 30 and 80 %, two years after planting. In the future, the post-Life monitoring planned to carry out a planting reinforcement. The stretches with hydromorphological restoration were colonized by pioneer herbaceous vegetation (ruderal species, including some invasive ones). It is interpreted as a first phase where opportunists dominate. In the coming years, a natural proliferation of riparian plants is expected to partially replace the pioneers.

The ecological monitoring carried out confirms how fluvial restoration is essential to increase the conservation status and the resilience capacity of riparian-fluvial ecosystems to global change. It is achieved through two strategies: (a) recover a natural fluvial dynamic: higher flows, fewer barriers and better sediment dynamics; (b) recover forests where there are none, through planting, and in the existing ones, improve their naturalness, maturity and heterogeneity, through silvicultural treatments.

The post-Life monitoring will allow evaluating the effect of the river restoration actions of LIFE ALNUS. Once floods are recorded in the Ter River (pilot project of Les Gambires and El Sorral Islands), it will be possible to analyse the morpho-sedimentary dynamics and evaluate the efficiency of hydromorphological and vegetation restoration. The mobility of vegetation remains after floods, the growth and vitality of alders and other riverside vegetation, as well as the success of the plantations, will also be analysed. Likewise, the response of the communities can be analysed in the medium-long term: aquatic macroinvertebrates, fish, flora and riverside vegetation, and semi-aquatic and riparian fauna.

2.

CHALLENGES FOR THE FUTURE

Submerged alder roots, a magnificent example of the association between forest and water (Fornès River, Ter basin) / Photo: Jordi Bas.

2. CHALLENGES FOR THE FUTURE

Listed below is a selection of the most important actions proposed by the LIFEALNUS discussion rooms. They address both the current and future challenges identified by social actors in the management and use of river ecosystems or fluvial areas.

- Implement a more adaptive management of fluvial areas. The recovery of natural dynamics is the solution for reducing flood risks, recovering floodplains and old river branches that help to relieve swelling rivers and reduce the impact of flooding on infrastructure. Incorporate global change scenarios (which predict a significant decrease in circulating flows) in the future dynamics of riparian forests.
- Active ecological restoration must be applied where necessary to recover and monitor natural processes: removal of locks and canals, fish passes, silvicultural actions, regulation of invasive species, hydromorphological and vegetation restoration. Promote the active management of sediments in locks and large reservoirs to facilitate the transportation of solids (pebbles, gravel, sand and mud), considering that both environmental flows and the transportation of sediments are essential for the maintenance of fluvial areas.
- The common goal of managers and users of fluvial areas is to restore the favourable ecological status of the riparian forest for ecosystem services, in compliance with the Habitats Directive and Water Framework Directive of the European Union. Compatibility must be ensured with other goals, such as timber production activities and public use.
- River courses are a strategic green infrastructure. It is necessary to manage their urban planning uses in accordance with their risks and environmental values. The aim should be to move towards removing buildings at high risk of flooding and that have a negative impact on the river.
- Promote river stewardship as a priority instrument for harmonising urban/agricultural management with the conservation of riverbanks and riverbeds. Offer incentives to landowners to extend riparian forest areas. Strike a balance between productive forest management and the presence of ecologically functional riparian forests of greater maturity and biodiversity. Options include fiscal measures, incentives for the adoption of good practices, and the facilitating river stewardship agreements.

Grey heron (*Ardea cinerea*) and cattle egret (*Bubulcus ibis*) nests in a alder forest in the Ter River in Torelló (Osona county) / Photo: Jordi Bas.

- Identify and recover stretches of old-growth riparian forests and in a good state of conservation in order to leave them to their natural dynamics and monitor them. They constitute highly functional and diverse benchmark systems for scientific monitoring and the application of management measures in multifunctional stretches.
- Increase knowledge (through pilot tests) of various fluvial area management measures in relation to their risks (sediments, timber drift, flooding) and the environmental services they provide. Furthermore, assess the implications of the good management of river functionality and of plant communities in reducing the risk of floods, establishing forest areas with different types of intervention in order to make the different uses compatible and with the goal of minimising the risks for infrastructure elements.
- Reach a consensus on easily applicable, crosscutting management guidelines for riparian forests. The guidelines must be related to the recovery of the functionality of riparian forests and biodiversity, to the strengthening of the resilience of riparian systems in the face of climate change and, therefore, to the regulation and minimisation of the risks associated with flooding.
- Undertake a study on the carrying capacity of riparian ecosystems in respect of different change factors, such as the degree of human presence in fluvial areas. The capacity should be calculated at a basin scale and local (municipal) scale, considering the specific characteristics of each stretch, suitable times of year for recreational activities and the periods of fragility for flora and fauna.
- Promote Basin Councils as entities that can foster collaborative work and the transfer and exchange of information on the management of fluvial areas between all the stakeholders.
- Draw up a training and dissemination plan for the management of fluvial areas aimed at politicians, technicians of public authorities, companies and organisations. The plan must include concepts such as riparian forest ecosystem services, tools to strike a balance between the environmental risks related to emergency events and the environmental benefits that high-quality riparian areas provide.
- Update public policies and legislation on the basis of all the new knowledge that is being generated related to a more integrated vision of fluvial dynamics.
- Launch citizen awareness campaigns to explain the importance of urban fluvial areas and the environmental benefits associated with the conservation of their natural values, especially the recovery of riparian forests. Involve citizens in the monitoring of projects carried out in fluvial areas through citizen science initiatives.
- Carry out long-term monitoring of restoration projects. Provide the financial resources to make them effective. Select pilot stretches to generate simple, small-scale hydrological and vegetation growth models, in order to facilitate understanding of the ecological dynamics of the riparian forest (regeneration, growth, maturity and decay) and of the associated biodiversity.

And you, what can you do?

Don't damage the plants or dispose of waste

Enjoy riverside areas with respect

Keep to the signposted tracks

Don't release any non-native fauna into the wild

Take part in volunteering campaigns

Report any offences affecting the natural or urban environment

GOOD STATE OF CONSERVATION

Illustration included in the brochure and in the LIFE ALNUS exhibition. Source: Anthesis Lavola.

3.

LEARNED LESSONS

White willow catkins (*Salix alba*) on the banks of the Segre River in Cerdanya. / Photo: Jordi Camprodon.

3. LEARNED LESSONS

We note the importance of investing efforts in preliminary studies. A precise cartographic information and data in the field was obtained for the design of a good strategy in the short and long term. This information was the basis for the conservation and restoration plans and to discuss the conservation actions and support the elaboration of the products of discussion, dissemination and transfer.

Spatial modelling is essential for planning a long-term conservation-restoration strategy at the basin level. It makes to optimize decision-making with regard to priority river stretches where to work efficiently. Different methods can be combined and compared. The models of eco-geographic indicators and those of systematic planning (Marxan software) and expert judgment are complementary.

The conservation and restoration plans are the basis for a long-term strategy, applicable in future projects carried out or financed by the environmental and fluvial administrations.

Despite the commendable effort made by the Catalan administration to protect the Natura 2000 network, LIFE ALNUS verified the lack of protection of river stretches with alder groves, as a habitat of priority interest. Previous studies evidenced the fragmentation and the scarce area occupied by the habitat in the alluvial plains, where it should find its maximum development and brightness.

Agreements with owners are basic, especially if a medium-long-term Stewardship Agreements can be made. Although rivers and their immediate riverbanks are defined as public domain by the Spanish water law, part of the actions may affect private property. Therefore, a good understanding with the owners that border the water bodies is necessary. It allows agreed planning, an execution of works without conflicts and facilitate the maintenance of works and the access to property to the monitoring actions.

The Catalan Water Agency, through the LIFE ALNUS, reached an agreement with the hydroelectric company Estabanell y Pahisa to release environmental flows in two weirs. It is an example of how the fluvial administration and the private company can reach agreements. It should be an example to be followed by other companies.

The river floods the entire alluvial plain in extraordinary floods. The project had to adapt to two extraordinary floods (Leslie and Gloria storms) during the action planning process. These great storms were a lesson to plan the restoration. To understand how the river works, it is essential to have previous hydromorphological studies and discussion with experts, including the experience of the local population living near the river.

In addition, the Leslie and Gloria storms served to discuss with the basin organizations about the management of plant remains after floods and the consequent development of technical precepts.

Throughout the project we discussed the best possible solutions to the challenges posed by river restoration. We start from the premise that the best restoration is to achieve natural dynamics. However, the rivers of the ALNUS basins are very humanized (for example, the Ter river has a weir almost every kilometer along its route). For this reason, normally only a very partial rehabilitation of natural processes is achieved. Bioengineering must be applied in the direction noted above. It can be used to protect the edges of the river, but in a very justified way, since artificially interfering with fluvial erosion goes against the natural dynamics.

Likewise, assess whether reforestation is necessary to restore riparian vegetation. Or, on the contrary, assess whether it is better to let the river rebuild the habitat by itself. The project chose to aid the river; for example, restoring the sediments extracted by previous human interventions. Later, it will be the river itself that ends up recovering the processes.

Planning when and where it was best to restore with planting was essential for greater success. Irrigation (accompanied by clearing of competing plants) made it possible to overcome periods of drought with less damage. Other key factors that were taken into account for the success of the plantation were: a) the correct selection of species according to the ecological season; b) to know the distribution of the water table and the structure of the soil (through previous studies or by expert criteria); and c) the local origin of the seeds and cuttings that were used to produce the plant in a specialized nursery of the public company Forestal Catalana.

The actions to improve the forest structure were useful above all to free riparian forests from exotic woody plants (prioritizing invasive ones) that

competed with the native ones. It is interesting to try treatment alternatives, including non-chemical treatments, to evaluate the best practices with the minimum economic and environmental cost.

A multidisciplinary ecological monitoring provided data from different indicator groups that were related to the structure of river habitats. They were useful to obtain a deeper understanding of the interrelationships between the river and living beings. The database obtained will allow future analyses, for example, to find out relationships between organisms.

Bioindicators react at different speeds to restoration actions. For example, macroinvertebrates and fish respond quickly, but riparian vegetation and fauna respond more slowly. Therefore, the monitoring is intended in the long term in the long term (post-Life). The high productivity of channels and riverbanks and the fluvial dynamics subjected to floods, allow the mobility of sediments and plant remains, vegetative growth and the response of bioindicators to be accelerated. Therefore, hydromorphological and vegetation monitoring should be carried out after floods. European funds are lacking to facilitate the continuity of post-Life monitoring.

The effects of recurrent droughts on the decline of alder and the colonization of different invasive herbaceous species, some of recent appearance, were verified. They are warnings of the effects of global change on riparian vegetation and put on the table the discussion of how to adapt these habitats to the new scenarios of the Anthropocene.

Dissemination must form an important part of the budget so that it has a real impact on the local population. If the LIFE ALNUS experience continues, investment will be made in new communication and museography technologies.

The bureaucratic slowness to achieve authorizations and tenders for restoration works and the long process of the technical-administrative reports (for example, the expansion of the Natura 2000 network) delayed the execution of some key actions for more than a year. The previous planning of the calendar of restoration projects must take this circumstance into account.

Multidisciplinary coordination and discussion to reach consensus between administrations (environmental, forestry and water management) and between these and civil society (stakeholders)

must be improved and strengthened. LIFE ALNUS tried to take participation very much into account and stimulated the debate on the good governance of fluvial areas. The discussion rooms, through a process of environmental mediation, were a good instrument to reach consensus. The resulting decalogues can be references to think about and apply strategies and action plans.

4.

RECOMMENDED READING

Grey herons (*Ardea cinerea*) nesting in an alder forest of the Ter River in Torelló / Photo: Jordi Bas.

4. RECOMMENDED READING

- / Calleja, J. A. 2009. *91E0 Bosques aluviales arbóreos y arborescentes de cursos generalmente altos y medios, dominados o codominados por alisos (Alnus glutinosa), fresnos de montaña (Fraxinus excelsior), abedules (Betula alba o B. pendula), avellanos (Corylus avellana) o álamos negros (Populus nigra) (*)*. Ministerio de Medio Ambiente, y Medio Rural y Marino. Madrid.

- / Camprodon, J., Ferreira, M. T., Ordeix, M. (eds.). 2012. *Restauración y gestión ecológica fluvial. Un manual de buenas prácticas de gestión de ríos y riberas*. Centre Tecnològic Forestal de Catalunya & ISA Press. Solsona – Lisboa.

- / Camprodon, J., Guardis, P., Ordeix, M. (eds.). 2022. *Technical handbook for the conservation and restoration of riparian areas. LIFE ALNUS*. Centre de Ciència i Tecnologia Forestal de Catalunya. Programa Life Natura i Biodiversitat de la Unió Europea.

- / Carreras, J., Ferré, J., Vigo, J. 2015. *Manual dels hàbitats de Catalunya. Volum VI. Boscos*. Generalitat de Catalunya, Departament de Territori i Sostenibilitat. Barcelona.

- / Elosegui, A., Sabater, S. (eds.). 2009. *Conceptos y técnicas en ecología fluvial*. Fundación BBVA. Bilbao.

- / Godé, L. (dir.). 2008. *La gestió i recuperació de la vegetació de ribera. Guia tècnica per actuacions en riberes*. Agència Catalana de l'Aigua. Departament de Medi Ambient i Habitatge de la Generalitat de Catalunya. Barcelona.

- / Lara, F., Garilleti, R., Calleja, J. A. 2004. *La vegetación de ribera de la mitad norte de España*. Centro de Estudios de Técnicas Aplicadas del CEDEX. Madrid.

- / Mola, I., Sopeña, A., de Torre, R. (eds.). 2018. *Guía Práctica de Restauración Ecológica*. Fundación Biodiversidad del Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica. Madrid.

- / Munné, A.; Prat, N., Ordeix, M., Puértolas, L., Rieradevall, M. 2009. *Els espais fluvials. Manual de diagnosi ambiental*. Obra Social “La Caixa” i Diputació de Barcelona. Barcelona.

- / Munné, A.; Solà, C., Pagès, J. (eds.). 2006. HIDRI. Protocol d'avaluació de la qualitat hidromorfològica dels rius. Agència Catalana de l'Aigua, Departament de Medi Ambient i Habitatge, Generalitat de Catalunya. Barcelona (disponible a <https://aca.gencat.cat/ca/laigua/seguiment-i-control/protocols>).

/ SER. 2019. *International principles and standards for the practice of ecological restoration*. Society for Ecological Restoration.

/ Vayreda, J., Comas, Ll., Guinart, D., Solórzano, S., Grau, J. 2022. *Manual de buenas prácticas forestales en espacios fluviales*. Parc Natural i Reserva de la Biosfera del Montseny. LIFE Tritó Montseny.

WEB SITES

/ AMBER river project: <https://amber.international/>

/ Atlas of barriers in European rivers: <https://amber.international/european-barrier-atlas/>

/ Blue rivers Foundation: <https://blueriversfoundation.org/>

/ Iberian Centre for River Restoration (CIREF): <https://cirefluvial.com>

/ Dam Removal Europe: <https://damremoval.eu/>

/ European Center for River Restoration: <https://www.ecrr.org/>

/ Open Rivers programme: restoring european rivers: <https://openrivers.eu/>

/ RiverWiki: https://restorerivers.eu/wiki/index.php?title=Main_Page

/ Society for Ecological Restoration: <https://www.ser.org/>

/ Wetlands International: <https://europe.wetlands.org>

www.lifealnus.eu

Collaborators

